

The Middle East: No Longer a Shatterbelt, Yet Still Divided¹

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Abstract

This article reexamines the contemporary geopolitical position of the Middle East through the lens of Saul Bernard Cohen's regional taxonomy, with particular emphasis on his concept of the shatterbelt and his post-Cold War claim that the structural conditions sustaining this status have begun to weaken. Cohen suggests that the erosion of symmetrical great-power rivalry has reduced the extent to which the region is primarily defined by external power competition, while internal dynamics have gained increasing significance. Although he does not codify this transformation into a distinct conceptual category, his reasoning opens analytical space for thinking about the Middle East in terms of an emerging – though still incomplete, process of regional systemic development. Building on this interpretation, the article critically reassesses the applicability of Cohen's diagnosis in light of subsequent developments, including post-Cold War and post-Arab Spring transformations of regional order. It advances the argument that while the Middle East no longer fulfills the core structural requirements of a classical shatterbelt, most notably sustained and symmetrical great-power rivalry – it also does not meet the criteria for what this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system: embryonic hierarchy, functional cohesion, institutional capacity, and relatively predictable interaction patterns. Instead of progressing toward systemic consolidation, the region remains marked by persistent fragmentation, episodic and reversible alliances, weak regional institutional architecture, and strategic indeterminacy. The analysis combines a historical reconstruction of the Middle East as a shatterbelt with a conceptual examination of contemporary regional dynamics and selected empirical illustrations. By revisiting Cohen's framework from a critical yet internal perspective, the article contributes to broader debates in political geography and geopolitical theory on regional transformation, post-hegemonic order, and the limits of system formation in deeply fragmented geopolitical environments.

Key Words:

Geopolitics, Middle East, Shatter Belt, Post-Hegemonic Order

¹ Editors note: Due to the fact that significant changes unfolded in the Middle East since the Workshop, editors have asked the author to revise the text.

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Introduction

The Middle East is frequently described in contemporary geopolitical literature as a region marked by profound historical layering, geographic heterogeneity, and persistent political fragmentation. From Napoleon's expedition to Egypt, through colonial reconfigurations, to successive postwar and late-Cold War transformations, as well as their post-Cold War legacies, the region has emerged as a near-permanent epicenter of global, regional, and internal tensions. Such a configuration has rendered it a paradigmatic example of what Saul Bernard Cohen conceptualizes as a "shatterbelt" – a region that is simultaneously deeply divided internally and persistently drawn into the rivalry of external geostrategic realms (Cohen, 1963; 1992).

Over nearly six decades of theoretical work, Cohen developed a distinctive geopolitical framework grounded in possibilism, the hierarchical interaction of geostrategic realms and geopolitical regions, and an analytical differentiation of spatial attributes and patterns shaping the relationships between political actors. Within this framework, the concept of the shatterbelt – first systematically articulated in "Geography and Politics in a World Divided" (1963) and subsequently refined in works published during the 1980s and 1990s, constitutes one of the most influential, yet also most contested, components of Cohen's theoretical legacy (Kopanja, 2020).

The notion of the shatterbelt emerged from a synthesis of Hartshorne's distinction between centrifugal and centripetal forces (Hartshorne, 1950 pp.106-110) and Cohen's ambition to integrate regionalist and systemic insights into a coherent geopolitical scheme (Kopanja, 2020, p.64-65). In this sense, a shatterbelt is defined as the outcome of the simultaneous operation of internal fragmentation and external competition among major geostrategic realms, with neither of these factors being sufficient on its own to account for its existence.

However, in his 1992 article "Middle East Geopolitical Transformation: The Disappearance of a Shatterbelt," Cohen advances the provocative claim that the Middle East no longer fulfills the core criteria of a shatterbelt. While this post-Cold War diagnosis suggests that the region has moved beyond the structural logic of the classical shatterbelt and entered a qualitatively different phase of regional evolution, a closer examination of contemporary structural patterns reveals serious limitations to such an interpretation. In order to examine this transformation more systematically, this article introduces the conceptual category of a "developing regional system", derived analytically from Cohen's broader geopolitical framework but not explicitly formulated by Cohen himself. As conceptualized here, a developing regional system presupposes the emergence of at least an embryonic regional hierarchy (see Ajzenhamer, 2019) – even when such a hierarchy remains

contested, unstable, or only partially consolidated, and also presupposes the gradual formation of more recurrent and predictable patterns of regional interaction and a minimum level of functional cohesion. These criteria provide the analytical benchmark against which the contemporary Middle East will be assessed in the following section.

Cohen implicitly suggested that the Middle East might, over time, begin to evolve toward a condition that this article will refer to as a developing regional system (Cohen, 1992, p. 2-3, 10): a regional configuration in which political dynamics are increasingly generated from within, while dependence on direct great-power rivalry progressively diminishes. Within Cohen's regional taxonomy, this regional configuration may be understood as an intermediate stage situated between the classical shatterbelt (and, in certain instances, pressure zones)³ on the one hand, and what he defines as gateway regions on the other – regions in which great powers eventually develop cooperative patterns of interaction that transform previously conflict-prone spaces into functional links between opposing geostrategic realms (Cohen, 2005, p. 4).

Building on this claim, present article first examines the historical formation of the Middle East as a shatterbelt, its position across different phases of the international system, and the reasons why the contemporary Middle East no longer conforms to Cohen's classical definition of a shatterbelt. It then considers whether the region may be approaching a condition that this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system. Finally, the article demonstrates that although the Middle East has clearly moved beyond the structural logic of the classical shatterbelt, it nevertheless fails to fit neatly into the ideal-typical model of what we define as a developing regional system.

The analysis combines a historical narrative of the region's colonial, Cold War, and post-Cold War transformations with Cohen's theoretical apparatus, drawing on both his seminal works and subsequent systematizations and reinterpretations of his conceptual framework.

³ It is important to clearly distinguish between Cohen's notion of a pressure zone and our concept of a developing regional system. A pressure zone refers to a region still primarily structured by external great-power pressures and lacking internal hierarchy, whereas a developing regional system denotes a phase in which external determination weakens and regional actors begin to generate their own relatively stable patterns of power and interaction, even though full systemic consolidation has not yet been achieved.

Setting the Geopolitical Stage and the Formation of the Shatterbelt

The emergence of the modern Middle East as a geopolitical region is commonly traced to Napoleon's expedition to Egypt in 1798, which for the first time in modern history opened the region to European powers as an arena of strategic competition. The French campaign marked a critical turning point at which the Middle East ceased to function merely as a peripheral extension of the Ottoman Empire and became a space of external power projection by European imperial actors (Rogan, 2005, pp. 18–22).

Within Cohen's theoretical vocabulary, this period represents the phase in which the region's core geopolitical attributes crystallized: strategic passages (most notably the future Suez Canal), trade routes, concentrated urban agglomerations, and boundaries that increasingly assumed the role of political-geographical nodes. As Kopanja emphasizes (2020), Cohen conceives geopolitical structures as shaped through the interaction of historical cores, political centers, ecumene, and "non-conforming zones," all of which were clearly present in the Middle East throughout the nineteenth century.

Through the expansion of British footholds in the Persian Gulf, the consolidation of control over the Suez Canal from 1875 onward, and the projection of maritime power, the region was incorporated into the maritime geostrategic realm as one of its key strategic segments. At the same time, Russia pursued access to the "warm seas," introducing a distinctive dual geopolitical tension into the region: internal fragmentation associated with the erosion of the Ottoman order and external competition among great powers.

It is precisely this conjunction of deep internal political fragmentation and strong external conditioning that constitutes the foundational pattern of the shatterbelt, as later systematized by Cohen in his theoretical framework.

The First World War brought about the final collapse of the Ottoman Empire and the establishment of the League of Nations mandate system, through which new state boundaries were drawn largely irrespective of existing social, ethnic, and religious configurations. Colonial interventions thus produced an ambivalent outcome: while enabling the formation of new political units, they simultaneously embedded enduring lines of division into the very foundations of the region's political geography (Rogan, 2005, pp. 23-36).

From a theoretical perspective, Cohen interprets the mandate system as a process through which external powers imposed geopolitical patterns that did not emerge from the region's internal dynamics. Cohen (1992) stresses that geopolitical patterns are formed through networks linking centers of power, corridors of movement, trade routes, and borders. In the Middle East, these networks did not arise through

endogenous regional evolution but were externally projected, contributing to a long-term deficit of cohesion. It is for this reason that Cohen identified the Middle East as one of the most “mature” examples of a shatterbelt.

Following the Second World War, accelerated decolonization neither eliminated deep internal fragmentations nor diminished the role of great powers in shaping regional relations (Slugett, 2005, pp. 50-54; Louis, 2004). Arab–Israeli conflicts, rivalries among Egypt, Iraq, and Iran, and the control of energy flows further entrenched the Middle East as a space in which internal conflicts readily spilled across state boundaries – a defining characteristic of the shatterbelt in Cohen’s theory.

Cohen defines a shatterbelt as a strategically oriented region that is simultaneously deeply divided internally and caught in competition between great powers of opposing geostrategic realms (1992, p.2, 9). The Middle East conformed fully to this description until the final decade of the Cold War. In Cohen’s model of the global geopolitical system, the Cold War is characterized by a clear hierarchical structure composed of two dominant geostrategic realms – the maritime realm led by the United States and the continental realm under Soviet leadership, between which a number of geopolitical regions were situated. Within this structure, the Middle East lay outside the core geostrategic centers of the great powers, remained exposed to continuous projections of their power, and persisted in a state of deep fragmentation driven by local rivalries. This combination rendered it a typologically near-ideal case of a shatterbelt.

In his work Cohen demonstrates that the regional wars of 1956, 1967, and 1973 possessed a dual structure: internal rivalries among states and societies were amplified by external interventions and bloc alignments (1992, p.4,7). During the Cold War, at least six centers of power – Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Israel, Iraq, and Turkey, operated within the Middle East, their interests frequently colliding. Cohen further emphasizes that shatterbelts are characterized by a low degree of cohesion and a high level of competition among subregional actors, a pattern that the Middle East fully exemplified during this period.

The Fading of the Shatterbelt: Post–Cold War Reconfigurations

In his 1992 article, Cohen advances the thesis that the end of the Cold War leads to a qualitative transformation of the Middle East as a geopolitical region. According to his interpretation, the region enters a phase in which classical great-power rivalry weakens and the autonomy of regional actors increases, pointing to the possibility of an evolution from a shatterbelt toward what this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system.

Our argument is grounded in Cohen's developmental model of the global geopolitical system, within which geopolitical regions move from a stage of atomization toward hierarchical integration once they succeed in internally shaping their own patterns of equilibrium. From this perspective, the Middle East in the early 1990s is viewed as a region gradually departing from the status of a shatterbelt and entering an early phase of autonomous regional systemic development.

The classical definition of a shatterbelt presupposes the existence of a clear external axis of great-power rivalry. After 1991, the United States remained the only global power with a full capacity for power projection (Sokolsky, 2003), while Russia and China retained only limited and selective presences in the region. As a result, the Middle East ceased to be embedded in a symmetrical competition between opposing geostrategic realms, which, according to Cohen's typology, constitutes a fundamental structural precondition of a shatterbelt.

As Kopanja notes (2020), in the post-Cold War phase Cohen further develops new analytical categories – pressure zones, convergence zones, and gateway regions, designed to capture spaces in which direct rivalry among global powers no longer takes place, yet where instability remains pronounced. The Middle East increasingly fits this logic: it remains highly conflict-prone, but ceases to function as a central mediator of conflict between opposing geostrategic realms.

Developments after 2003, including the Iraq War, the processes triggered by the Arab Spring in 2011, and the rise of regional actors such as Turkey, Iran, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates, further consolidated a configuration in which internal actors assume primacy in shaping regional dynamics (Alakel & Arab, 2025; Katz, 2025). External actors continue to exert significant influence, but the region is no longer structured around a clearly defined bipolar axis of conflict.

This evolution represents a substantial departure from Cohen's original definition of the shatterbelt, in which internal conflicts acquire full structural significance only in conjunction with intense and symmetrical external rivalry among great powers. In the contemporary context, the Middle East remains a highly conflictual space, yet it is increasingly difficult to describe it as a shatterbelt in the classical Cohenian sense and increasingly appropriate to view it as a complex and multipolar regional order in the making.

Cohen's 1992 claim that the Middle East had exited the status of a shatterbelt thus marked an important theoretical shift in the understanding of regional dynamics. According to his model, a shatterbelt can persist only so long as two structural conditions are simultaneously fulfilled: intense and relatively symmetrical penetration by great powers of opposing geostrategic realms, and deep internal fragmentation that renders the region persistently vulnerable. In the contemporary Middle Eastern context, both of these conditions have been weakened or

transformed. The region no longer fits the matrix of a bipolar international system, while internal actors have acquired growing autonomy in defining the directions of regional security.

Nevertheless, while the Middle East no longer conforms to Cohen's classical conception of a shatterbelt, the question arises as to whether it can develop the structural coherence, internal hierarchy, and functional autonomy necessary to be regarded as what this article terms a developing regional system.

A Regional System? Not Yet

Although Cohen's post-Cold War diagnosis suggests that the Middle East has moved beyond the status of a shatterbelt and entered a phase resembling what this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system, a closer examination of contemporary structural patterns reveals serious limitations to such an interpretation. Consistent with Cohen's broader theoretical framework, a developing regional system would presuppose the emergence of at least an embryonic regional hierarchy – even if such a hierarchy remains contested, unstable, or still in formation. In the Middle East, however, the presence of multiple regional power aspirants does not translate into a hierarchical order, but rather into a condition of persistent multipolar instability. Turkey, Iran, Saudi Arabia, and Israel possess substantial military, political, and economic capabilities, yet there is neither a minimal consensus regarding the legitimacy of their respective roles nor agreement on the boundaries of their influence (Alakel & Arab, 2025). The absence of an actor capable of stabilizing the regional order or imposing broadly accepted patterns of behavior prevents the consolidation of an internal power structure into a systemic form.

Empirically, this fragmentation of hierarchy is clearly observable in the case of Syria, which increasingly functions less as an arena of direct great-power rivalry and more as a “stress test” of a disrupted regional balance of power. Following the fall of Bashar al-Assad and the takeover of central authority by Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) under Abu Mohammad al-Julani, Russia has adopted a restrained posture, focusing primarily on the preservation of its military facilities in Tartus and Hmeimim, while the United States exercises a mediating and verification-oriented role rather than direct strategic control. The core dynamics are instead generated by regional actors – most notably Israel, Turkey, and local forces, but in the absence of any shared regulatory framework capable of translating their competition into a stable regional hierarchy.

This structural deficit is further compounded by the prevailing patterns of interaction among regional actors. Within international relations theory and

geopolitical analysis alike, a region attains the quality of a “system” only when its actors exhibit recurring and relatively predictable patterns of cooperation and rivalry. The contemporary Middle East, by contrast, is characterized by ad hoc, instrumental, and reversible alliances, as well as multilayered and overlapping rivalries in which the same actors simultaneously function as partners and adversaries across different security, political, and economic domains. The dynamics of Israeli-Turkish competition in Syria are illustrative in this respect. Turkey’s military presence in northern Syria, its efforts to complete the containment of Syrian Kurdish actors and to support the new Syrian regime, as well as Israel’s preventive strikes against infrastructure formerly linked to Tehran – now perceived as a “portal” through which Ankara seeks to project its military power, derive from autonomous national strategies, yet fail to generate stable and predictable patterns of regional interaction. Rather than producing systemic cohesion, these dynamics result in a condition of persistent strategic fragmentation (Hazbun, 2018).

At the same time, the process of regional fragmentation has undergone a transformation. While the bloc-based fragmentation characteristic of the Cold War shatterbelt has faded, it has been replaced by deeper and more resilient forms of stratification. Contemporary conflicts are rooted in sectarian, ethnic, regime-based, and sub-state divisions that permeate the region and generate persistent political instability. In a developing regional system, fragmentation weakens in structural terms even when conflicts persist; in the Middle East, however, fragmentation remains systemic, albeit no longer organized around a single external axis – whether the U.S.–Soviet confrontation or subsequent U.S. balancing vis-à-vis Iran.

The absence of functional regional cohesion further reinforces this diagnosis. Although our concept does not require a high degree of institutionalization, a developing regional system presupposes at least a minimal capacity of the region to generate its own mechanisms of conflict management, normative coordination, and long-term alignment of interests. In the Middle East, however, regional institutions and forums lack the structural weight necessary to perform these functions, preventing the region from “carrying itself” as a system independently of external interventions.

By way of illustration, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) functions primarily as an interest-based forum of wealthy Arab petro-monarchies and as an anti-Iranian alignment, rather than as an institutional representative of the geopolitical interests or strategic autonomy of the region as a whole (Kilibarda, Mladenović& Ajzenhamer, 2013). Conversely, the Arab League remains deeply embedded in a predominantly Westphalian logic: its member states prioritize the preservation of sovereign autonomy over the advancement of collective security, thereby severely limiting the organization’s integrative and regulatory capacity. Moreover, beyond ad hoc initiatives – such as the Baghdad Conference for Cooperation and Partnership

launched in 2021, there exists no adequate, exclusively regional framework capable of institutionalizing sustained cooperation among the key regional actors, including the Arab petro-monarchies, Iran, and Turkey. The absence of such a forum further underscores the lack of functional cohesion required for the consolidation of a developing regional system.

The security dilemma remains the dominant pattern of behavior. In a developing regional system, security ceases to operate exclusively according to a zero-sum logic and is partially replaced by pragmatic forms of cooperation and risk management. In the Middle East, however, security perceptions remain existentialized, military force retains a central role in political communication, and escalation remains a constantly available option. The Iranian–Israeli escalation during and after the 2023 Gaza war clearly illustrates this dynamic (Aldalala’a & Shukri, 2025). Military strikes, missile responses, and the spillover of violence into Lebanon, Iraq, and Syria unfolded on the basis of autonomous regional security calculations by Iran and Israel, while the United States responded belatedly, inconsistently, and without a coherent hegemonic strategy (Ajzenhamer, 2025a; Pratiwi, Qomara, & Syarafi, 2020). This pattern of behavior confirms that the region is no longer stabilized by an external regulator, yet simultaneously demonstrates that internal dynamics do not generate the degree of systemic discipline necessary for the consolidation of a developing regional system (Nowacka, 2023).

The same logic is observable beyond regional conflict arenas, becoming evident in extra-regional crises.

A further indication of the erosion of external hegemonic discipline can be observed in the positioning of the Gulf states toward the war in Ukraine. From the moment Russia recognized the self-proclaimed republics of Donetsk and Luhansk, Gulf actors adopted differentiated and carefully calibrated responses, revealing a broader pattern of strategic hedging rather than alignment (Szalai, 2023). Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Qatar publicly supported diplomatic efforts aimed at de-escalation, yet refrained from explicitly condemning Russia’s invasion of Ukraine or joining Western sanctions regimes. Notably, the United Arab Emirates – then holding a temporary seat on the United Nations Security Council, twice abstained from votes aimed at holding Russia accountable and condemning its military actions.

Qatar adopted a more explicit rhetorical stance in support of Ukrainian sovereignty, yet similarly avoided participation in sanctions. At the same time, none of these states recognized the separatist entities in eastern Ukraine, and all ultimately supported the UN General Assembly resolution condemning the invasion and calling for the withdrawal of Russian forces. This pattern reflects a deliberate strategy of hedging – signaling continued partnership with the United States while simultaneously preserving strategic autonomy vis-à-vis Russia.

From a regional-systemic perspective, such behavior is highly indicative. It demonstrates that the United States no longer possesses the capacity to enforce alignment or discipline even among its closest Middle Eastern partners. Yet this erosion of hegemonic authority does not translate into the emergence of a coherent regional order. Instead, it reinforces a condition in which regional actors pursue autonomous and interest-driven positioning without converging toward shared norms, hierarchies, or institutionalized coordination. As such, the weakening of U.S. hegemonic influence contributes not to regional system consolidation, but to a prolonged phase of strategic indeterminacy.

This dynamic is further compounded by the multiplication of subregional centers of power – including a now significantly weakened Hezbollah, Iraqi Shi‘a militias, the Houthis, and various Syrian factions, which further fragments the regional space and undermines the possibility of its hierarchical consolidation. Empirical accounts of episodes such as the so-called “twelve-day war” involving Iran, Israel, and the United States, in which military strikes, unilateral (and largely symbolic) declarations of victory, and calls for restraint followed one another in rapid succession and without a clear systemic framework, point to the absence of a stable external hegemonic architecture as well as to the region’s inability to generate a sustainable order on its own (Ajzenhamer, 2025b).

Finally, the problem of insufficient regional systematization is also reflected in the indeterminate spatial boundaries of the region.⁴ A developing regional system presupposes a relatively clear differentiation between core and periphery, as well as limited and manageable zones of overlap. By contrast, the Middle East is characterized by fluid and overlapping spatial configurations encompassing the Levant, the Persian Gulf, the Eastern Mediterranean, and the Red Sea, within which centers of power are dispersed in an essentially anarchic manner. This spatial indeterminacy further undermines the consolidation of the region as a coherent system.

In this sense, from a geopolitical perspective, the contemporary Middle East occupies a theoretical interstitial space between the two Cohenian concepts under discussion: it no longer fulfills the structural conditions of a classical shatterbelt, yet it simultaneously lacks the hierarchy, cohesion, and predictability that we associate with a developing regional system.

Concluding Remarks

⁴ An illustrative example of this spatial indeterminacy is the fact that Israel today is no longer surrounded exclusively by traditional Arab neighbors. As a consequence of Turkey’s entrenched military and political presence in northern Syria, Israel has, in a de facto geopolitical sense, acquired Turkey as an additional “neighboring” regional power, despite the absence of any de jure border between the two states. For a broader discussion of Israel’s evolving border environment, see Cohen (2020).

This study has taken as its point of departure Cohen's post-Cold War thesis that, by the late twentieth century, the Middle East had ceased to function as a shatterbelt and had begun a transition toward a developing regional system. The analysis of the region's historical formation as a shatterbelt, its role within the Cold War structure of the international system, and contemporary patterns of regional dynamics has enabled a critical reassessment of this claim. The central finding may be summarized as follows: the contemporary Middle East no longer fulfills the structural conditions of a classical shatterbelt, yet it likewise does not possess the key characteristics that we associate with a developing regional system. The region therefore occupies a theoretical intermediate position between these two ideal-typical models.

Historical analysis has shown that, throughout the nineteenth and much of the twentieth century, the Middle East corresponded closely to Cohen's definition of a shatterbelt. Deep internal fragmentation, combined with intense and symmetrical external penetration by great powers, rendered the region particularly sensitive to global shifts in power. During the Cold War, the Middle East was firmly embedded within the hierarchical structure of the bipolar international system, with local conflicts regularly amplified and redirected through external intervention and bloc alignment. In this period, the region constituted an almost paradigmatic empirical example of a shatterbelt in Cohen's theoretical sense.

However, the end of the Cold War produced profound changes in the external structure of regional security (Katz, 2025). The weakening of symmetrical great-power competition, the disappearance of a bipolar axis of rivalry, and the increasing autonomy of regional actors have undermined the sustainability of the shatterbelt model. As demonstrated in the analysis, the contemporary Middle East is no longer a space in which global rivalries are systematically refracted through local conflicts. External powers retain significant influence, but they no longer structure the region through a clearly defined and stable hierarchy. In Cohen's typology, this fulfills the first major condition for transcending the shatterbelt.

Yet the analysis has also shown that a weakening of external determination does not automatically lead to the consolidation of a regional system. A developing regional system, as we understand it, presupposes at least an embryonic hierarchy, recurring interaction patterns, functional cohesion, and a capacity for internally generated stabilizing mechanisms. In the Middle East, none of these elements are sufficiently developed. Instead of a hierarchical order, the region exhibits persistent multipolarity without consensus regarding the legitimacy or scope of regional influence of key actors.

Empirical findings consistently indicate the absence of structural preconditions for systemic consolidation. Although reduced external determinism has enabled greater autonomy for regional actors, this autonomy has not resulted in the formation of a

stable hierarchy or recognizable order. Regional dynamics remain largely unregulated and fragmented, while competition unfolds without mechanisms capable of translating it into systemic equilibrium. Rather than stabilizing, autonomous action produces prolonged strategic uncertainty (Hazbun, 2018).

This outcome is closely linked to interaction patterns that remain episodic and context-dependent. Alliances are temporary and instrumental, rivalries multilayered and fluid, and the roles of individual actors vary across issue areas. Such a configuration does not generate predictability or normative expectations but sustains a condition of enduring strategic fragmentation incompatible with Cohen's notion of regional systemhood.

At the same time, fragmentation has not disappeared but has assumed new, deeper forms. With the decline of Cold War bloc divisions, the region did not enter a phase of structural homogenization. Instead, it has remained stratified along sectarian, ethnic, regime-based, and sub-state lines. These forms of fragmentation have become durable features of regional politics and constitute an internal obstacle to systemic consolidation, independent of the external constellation of power.

The institutional dimension reinforces this conclusion. Existing regional organizations lack the capacity to function as vehicles of collective security or long-term coordination of interests. They remain either constrained by the interests of narrow groups of actors or bound by the sovereignty-centered logic of their member states, without the ability to generate functional cohesion at the regional level. The absence of an inclusive, stable regional format encompassing key actors further limits prospects for systemic consolidation.

The security dimension is particularly illustrative. The persistence of the security dilemma, the existentialization of threat perceptions, and continued reliance on military force as a primary instrument of political communication indicate that the region has not moved into a phase in which conflicts are managed through institutionalized or normatively stabilized mechanisms. Actor autonomy does not produce self-regulation but sustains a high level of instability.

Additionally, the weakening of external hegemonic discipline – observable even beyond the immediate regional context, does not lead to the emergence of an alternative regional order. Instead, it prolongs a condition of strategic indeterminacy in which regional actors operate autonomously, yet without converging toward shared rules, hierarchies, or institutionalized coordination.

Finally, the spatial indeterminacy of the region further undermines its systemic articulation. The overlap of multiple subregional spaces and the absence of a clear differentiation between core and periphery prevent the formation of a stable

regional framework. Under such conditions, the Middle East remains an open and fragmented space, unable to consolidate into a coherent regional system.

Taken together, these findings indicate that the contemporary Middle East constitutes a theoretical interstitial space between shatterbelt and developing regional system. It has moved beyond the logic of the shatterbelt but has not entered the phase of a developing regional system. This ambivalent position renders the region analytically challenging and underscores the need to reinterpret, rather than abandon, Cohen's framework – adapting it to the structural realities of current Middle Eastern dynamics.

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